

A Reliable Interest Point Detection

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Abstract

Interest point detection is a fundamental task in computer vision, with applications in image matching, 3D reconstruction, and image stitching. Traditional methods often produce numerous weak and unstable keypoints that are sensitive to noise, viewpoint changes, and illumination variations, adversely affecting subsequent tasks like matching and reconstruction. To mitigate this, a deep learning architecture incorporating dual-network detection consistency is proposed. This approach integrates two independent detection networks and employs a consensus mechanism, retaining only the keypoints identified by both networks to filter out unreliable candidates. Experimental results demonstrate that this framework achieves an average matching accuracy of 90% on the HPatches dataset, surpassing the overall performance of current mainstream algorithms.

Keywords: Interest Point Detection, Dual-Network Consistency, Image Matchine, Keypoint Filtering, Weak Keypoint Suppression

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1. Introduction

Interest point detection is fundamental in computer vision, yet traditional methods often yield weak keypoints sensitive to noise, viewpoint, and illumination changes, degrading matching and reconstruction performance. With the rise of deep learning, CNN-based detectors have become mainstream. For instance, FAST improved upon the SUSAN detector, while LIFT, SuperPoint, R2D2, D2-Net, and Key.Net advanced joint detection and description under various learning schemes [1–15]. Additionally, self-supervised approaches like Deep Corner and equivariant learning have enhanced robustness using corner characteristics and rotational invariance [16–27]. However, these methods still face challenges in suppressing weak keypoints in complex scenarios, limiting matching accuracy and overall performance [28–30].

To address the issue of weak and unstable keypoints, we propose a robust detection method based on dual-network consensus filtering. This approach employs two independent detectors and retains only keypoints mutually agreed upon by both networks, effectively suppressing unreliable points and enhancing stability. As shown in Fig. ??, detections from MS-R2D2 and REKD are filtered via consensus, yielding a sparser, more reliable keypoint set. Experimental results demonstrate our method’s superior stability and matching accuracy under affine transformations, noise, and tasks like 3D reconstruction.

2. Proposed Method

This work introduces a robust interest-point detection method built on a dual-network architecture that integrates an enhanced multi-scale R2D2

(MS-R2D2) with REKD. MS-R2D2 extends the original R2D2 by incorporating a multi-scale feature fusion mechanism, which explicitly combines shallow and deep features to improve adaptability to scale variations and complex scenes [?]. REKD employs rotation-equivariant convolutions to ensure consistent performance under rotational transformations [31–37]. This combination provides complementary strengths—encompassing both detection and description while addressing robustness to scale and rotation. Augmented by a dual-network consensus filtering mechanism, the approach effectively suppresses weak keypoints, thereby enhancing the overall precision and reliability of interest-point detection.

2.1. Multi-Scale R2D2 (MS-R2D2)

Building upon the deep, self-supervised R2D2 framework for joint keypoint detection and description, we introduce MS-R2D2. As illustrated in Fig. ??, it enhances the original model by incorporating a multi-scale feature fusion mechanism to boost matching robustness and accuracy.

Based on an L2-Net backbone, MS-R2D2 extracts features from shallow, middle, and deep stages. These multi-scale features are progressively fused via 1×1 convolutions and upsampling. Three parallel heads are then attached: a descriptor head for 128-D L2-normalized descriptors, a repeatability head for a saliency heatmap, and a reliability head for pixel-wise stability weights. The final keypoint score is the product of repeatability and reliability, with optimal keypoints selected via local maxima detection.

By explicitly integrating multi-scale information, MS-R2D2 enhances robustness to scale changes and complex scenes, improving both the localization of small structures and the stability of larger-scale patterns compared to the

original R2D2 [?].

2.2. REKD

Based on a rotation-equivariant convolutional neural network, REKD is a self-supervised method that detects oriented interest points. Its core innovation lies in using rotation-equivariant convolutions to ensure detection consistency under in-plane rotations, significantly enhancing robustness. Instead of directly predicting orientations, REKD learns a histogram-based orientation representation trained with a dense orientation-alignment loss [?].

2.3. Dual-Network Consensus Filtering

Based on a dual-network architecture (MS-R2D2 and REKD), a consensus filtering mechanism is designed to suppress weak, spurious, or redundant keypoints caused by challenging conditions like illumination changes, rotation, and scale variation. The two networks are trained concurrently to leverage their complementary strengths, enhancing detection accuracy and consistency.

The core idea is to run these structurally different networks in parallel on the same image and select stable interest points based on their spatial agreement and response scores. This “dual-network consensus” acts as a self-check: consistent high responses for robust features across both models help suppress model-specific false detections.

The concrete procedure involves:

1. **Score-map generation:** Each network produces an interest-point score map where pixel values indicate saliency.

2. **Keypoint extraction:** Local maxima are identified from each score map to get keypoint coordinates.
3. **Euclidean distance computation:** For each candidate keypoint pair from the two networks, the Euclidean distance between their coordinates is calculated. Keypoints are subsequently filtered based on spatial proximity and their response scores:

$$d(p_1, p_2) = \|p_1 - p_2\|_2. \quad (1)$$

4. **Strong-corner selection:** If the inter-network distance is below a preset threshold, the two detections are deemed consistent and the keypoint is retained.

Joint training combined with this consensus rule suppresses false and unstable detections, yielding a highly reliable and stable set of interest points. The complete architecture, outlined in Fig. ??, shows the parallel score-map generation and the subsequent filtering flow.

2.4. Co-Training and Joint Loss Function

To enable synergistic optimization of the two networks, we adopt a joint loss to guide training. The key to co-training is to share information and feedback so that, while learning independently, the two models reinforce each other, thereby improving the precision and robustness of the final detections. The loss design addresses four aspects: repeatability, descriptor matchability, rotational consistency, and consensus filtering:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{rep}} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{desc}} + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{\text{rot}} + \lambda_4 \mathcal{L}_{\text{cons}}. \quad (2)$$

3. Experimental Results and Analysis

Experiments on the HPatches dataset demonstrate that the proposed method achieves an average matching accuracy of 90%, surpassing the overall performance of mainstream algorithms under affine transformations, noise, and 3D reconstruction settings [38].

4. Conclusion

We presented a robust interest-point detection method based on Dual-Network Consensus Filtering (DNCF), which couples an improved Multi-Scale R2D2 (MS-R2D2) with REKD. By leveraging their complementary strengths—scale robustness from MS-R2D2 and rotational robustness from REKD—and by employing co-training with consensus filtering, the proposed approach effectively suppresses weak keypoints. Compared with the original R2D2, MS-R2D2 introduces explicit multi-scale feature fusion within the network, yielding more stable detections under scale changes and in complex scenes; its integration with REKD further enhances rotational invariance. By filtering the two networks’ score maps and keypoint coordinates via Euclidean-distance consensus, weak keypoints are removed while reliable ones are retained. Experiments on multiple standard datasets demonstrate superior robustness and higher matching accuracy under affine transformations, noise, image matching, and 3D reconstruction.

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